

Use of Authentic Learning Tools in Delivery of Scientific Education

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Abstract—Authentic learning is the technique used in education institutes of all levels to help the students understand concepts by linking academic concepts with real-world scenarios. The use of e-learning is found very useful in conveying ideas with visual and vocal methods. Integrating e-learning and authentic learning creates a new paradigm of learning beneficial to both the teachers and students in knowledge sharing. This study deals with the significance of authentic learning in e-learning framework. A prototype application is developed to convey knowledge to the participants, and further analysis of understanding is made using a survey questionnaire. The survey is based on a set of parameters to analyze the remembering and understanding outcome of participating individuals against their age, prior experience and educational level. The results show consistency for all the factors, showing the effectiveness of e-learning tools and authentic learning methods.

Keywords - *E-Learning; Higher Education; Teaching Methods*

I. INTRODUCTION

Authentic learning is used in education and tuition techniques to help the students in connecting what they learn in the school to the problems, issues, and concepts they face in the real world. Several definitions of authentic learning are present in the literature. Authentic learning is defined by Hawland and co-authors [1] as “learning that is seamlessly integrated or implanted into meaningful, ‘real-life’ situations”. For Revington [2], authentic learning means “real-life learning”. It is a style of learning that inspires students to create a concrete, useful product to be shared with their world”. Authentic learning was defined by Har [3] as an academic approach that involves the students in solving real-world problems. Some of the authentic learning activities include role-playing, project-based learning, learning by doing, and problem-based learning. Authentic learning provides better learning opportunities, helps in a better understanding of a complex concept, prepares the learner for a better future, and blends learning and theories.

Authentic learning uses technology and different education tools to deliver knowledge. Some analysts [4] [5] consider authentic learning as one of the instructional approaches that bring real-world experiences inside the classroom. To date, several studies have merged authentic learning into learning and teaching techniques [6-11]. Nevertheless, educators still face a significant challenge to practice authentic learning via technology. E-learning uses an authentic approach to increase its efficiency, and an authentic learning environment creates

new techniques by using e-learning tools. It is necessary here to clarify what exactly is meant by e-learning. Moreno and Mayer [12] define e-learning as the use of electronic technologies for creating a link with classroom and material learned even outside of a classroom.

Basis of authentic learning is on a simple idea: designing an environment that is close to the real environment improving learning. Recently, teaching techniques that do not follow this basic idea are considered ineffective in education. With the advancement in technology (visualization and simulation) and different internet applications, the implementation of authentic learning environments is encouraged, making a bridge between classroom learning and real-world [5]. Various disciplines have reported the successful implementation of authentic learning environments, including history [13], economics [14], literature [15], and biology [16]. Technology use in the classroom helps in designing learning activity, its assessment, supporting context, exploring knowledge, solving real-world problems, and meditating communication and collaboration [17].

A. Structure

In recent years, there has been an augmented interest in e-learning, and there is a preference by both academics and students [18]. Arbaugh [19] mentions that several e-learning factors and the authentic learning dimensions are overlapping (student, educator, course, technology, system design, and proper environment development). E-learning and authentic learning boost computer skills, reception of versatile feedback, teamwork, flexibility, discussion sessions, content quality, material availability, and promotion of higher cognition [20]. This article focuses on a critical aspect that e-learning and authentic learning are different; authentic learning is an approach rather than a tool.

Authentic learning focuses on the solution to complex problems students would face in the real world; this creates an environment in which learners encourage skills like complex communication and higher-order analysis that supports them in the real world [5, 21]. The author in [22] writes, “It is this ability to identify and solve problems using recognition and metacognition that sets apart those with skills to help them advance in their careers from those who have little opportunity to move forward,” supporting the views presented earlier. Authentic learning opposes the idea that every problem can be solved by memorizing the right answers [5]. The authentic environment allows the students to learn in a situation closed to

the one they face in a professional setting, making learners confident. One of the features of an authentic environment is to provide the learner with authentic activities [23].

Furthermore, it must be able to deliver multiple functions and diverse perceptions in studies [24]. Brown [25] mentions that the authentic learning environment encourages group work and concept exchange that enhances cognitive abilities. Another trait of an authentic learning environment is the provision of expert's opinion, processes, and designing of the operations [26]. An authentic learning environment helps to make the students independent by using the scaffolding and fading of the mentor technique [27].

To validate the authentic learning in an educational setting, many educational psychologists and researchers have attempted to work on different criteria and ideas to date. Authors in [21] identified the availability of the authentic context as one of the most important criteria. Others have highlighted expert performance as the commonly used approach. Students can use online tools that allow them to assume the role of the teacher in organizing the classroom, learning methods and experiences, and how students receive a response in the classroom [28]. One of the other approaches to learning is collaboration. The author presents that students that work in a team can solve any problem more effectively as the discussion about the problem helps a lot in learning concepts [29]. Another technological approach towards learning mentioned by Lee quoting Vygotsky, saying, "Thought undergoes many changes as it turns into speech. It does not merely find expression in speech; it finds reality and form." [30]. Practically put forward by Hoban and Ferry in their publication [31], presented a slow-motion animation as a tool, and selected a student to make comments about it. Afterwards, explaining the idea of the slow-motion video to other students, the selected student comprehends it first.

B. Literature Review

In literature, Herrington points out the importance of authentic learning in his book "A practical guide to authentic e-learning," by negating the objections against the authentic learning in higher education [32]. The author stated that the integration of authentic e-learning is accessible in higher education institutes that have already adapted the computer and web-based communication with students. The environment can improve student-learning conditions using the e-learning domain. However, the change will be gradual, and regular updates can be a long-lasting and sustainable authentic e-learning system. The idea is further enhanced by Chang and co-authors in their book on "Authentic learning through Advances in technology," with the development of newer and task-oriented devices, much better support for learning and transformation is expected [33]. It is postulated that with the initial slow pace of induction, the future students will be able to acquire things much quicker than conceivable for the present generation. Although the speed in acquiring knowledge is necessary since, with the increasing volume of knowledge, there is a need for learning fast and learning in-depth. Authentic learning is also very crucial in developing innovative minds at the higher education level. Herrington [34] mentioned the effectiveness of technology in the field of higher education.

The research suggested that authentic learning can bring innovation in design and creation with its real-life learning opportunities. A supporting opinion is presented by Churchill [35], stating, "Technology amplifies our intellectual and physical capacity," presented a similar idea for a lower level of educational institutes. The author stressed the importance of technology at the secondary school level. However, the quantitative importance of authentic learning at the secondary school level was presented by Preus [36], stating an improvement in performance from 30 to 60 percentiles. There is also a need to not just focus on the authentic education mode of delivery, but the focus should also be on the valuation of knowledge, and that also needs to be authentic at all education levels. Investigators mark this method of learning as an authentic assessment [37]. So, combining the authentic mode of delivery and authentic assessment of knowledge fulfils the conditions for best practices [38, 39].

The importance of authentic learning and technology is significant from the work of numerous researchers. Bozalek [40] remarked that there is a symbiotic relationship between technological advancements and authentic learning where authentic learning goes hand in hand with the use of technology, enabling the sharing of ideas and collaborations in fields that are changing continuously. Authentic learning is the perfect alignment for the progress of the educational field. However, to fulfil the goals of this alignment, there is a need for a link between technology and education. The reason the current system is lagging this synergy because there is a need for collaborative efforts by specialists in technology and communication [41]. All of this, despite that authentic learning, is very appealing to those since it links the knowledge to real scenarios creating a better conceptual understanding and thereby solving the problems [42].

What we need to reach the essence of authentic learning is to give problem-solving skills to the students through a thought-provoking process. The problems presented will be from real-world context, making students think like professionals [43]. Though, for this, there is a need for spending time and effort on real-time problem solving and innovative challenges in the higher education domain rather than spending valuable time on unnecessary tasks [44]. In John Seeley and Allan Collins' opinion, authentic learning methods are "not just beneficial; they are crucial" [45]. Still, the problem existing in the current system is that despite knowing the importance of technology and authentic learning, students are deprived of an authentic environment because of the cost associated with it [46]. The old and less enlightening syllabus makes the students follow lab guides making the slightest logical investigation. The exams are passed through cramming, while experimental testing is plagiarized, all to pass the system and get a job [47].

II. METHODOLOGY

The study uses quantitative analysis to gain insights into the principle of authentic learning and evaluation of the feedback from the respondents to articulate findings. This study presents the authentic environment in the form of a software application (prototype) called the authentic lab. The prototype was

designed and developed on the principle of authentic learning by introducing the learner with the real-life example of the concepts; corresponding this authentic concept, the survey questions were designed on the real-life examples that were presented in the prototype. This way, the questions evaluated the efficacy of authentic attributes' inclusion in the prototype by questioning the parameters of the real world. The participants in the survey based on their experience and learning, try to comprehend the problem presented. The survey investigates the understanding and ability to remember the concepts discussed in the prototype. The application then provides a visual explanation of the idea. The information is kept concise and straightforward, so the user creates a better understanding of the concepts based on presented infographics. As mentioned before, this manuscript undertakes the evaluation of the user experiences with the software application based on a survey that is conducted after the user goes through the application learning cycle. The effectiveness of the prototype is presented in the results in the form of a survey evaluation.

The prototype application is based on four basic scientific concepts, developed, and placed on four different screens. The prototype development was aimed to focus on the learning content, its presentation, and the measurement of the recorded responses. The first concept in the prototype was named "Egg Float Test." The main screen of the concept presentation asked the user if he/she knows the difference between a healthy and rotten chicken egg. Video aids and graphics were provided on the next screens. This concept aimed to supply information about Hydrogen, connecting the scientific knowledge about Hydrogen in a real-world problem. The second concept was "Paper Bag Magic," to deliver information about Hydrogen. The "Save Green Vegetables" concept was used in the prototype to help the users learn about Magnesium, and the "Car Screens" concept aimed to make the user learn about greenhouse gasses. The extent of understanding was later recorded in the survey.

III. FEEDBACK SURVEY METHODOLOGY

A survey was conducted to measure the efficacy of an authentic learning-based e-learning framework at The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia. A random sample of 98 students participated in the study. A small sample was chosen because of the expected difficulty in obtaining feedback from all students. The participants were recruited from different educational backgrounds and levels of education (Undergraduates to PhD students). The age of the contributors ranged from 18 to 38 years. All the respondents were presented with the participant information sheet. All the participants agreed to the terms of participating in the survey. The efficiency of the application was assessed to deliver the educational concepts based on real-life examples, an essential idea of authentic learning, by developing a questionnaire to cross-examine the prior knowledge, understanding level, and extent of accommodation of the concept presented in Authentic Lab. The first step was the testing of authentic learning elements to interrogate the following areas:

- Component to be tested: Sustained investigation (of scientific concepts)

- Did the student find it easy to use?
- Did the student understand the concept of the experiment? (qualitative or quantitative measurement)
- Did the respondent found it easy to remember the idea? (qualitative or quantitative analysis)

The survey conducted in this study was comprised of 14 questions. The questions included in the survey are listed in **Error! Reference source not found.** As mentioned in the literature review, the authentic learning environment is based on real-world problems; all the items are constructed and framed on the same concept. All the survey questions utilized a 5-point Likert scale. There were four basic concepts discussed in this prototype. The list of items from question 2 to question 13 was corresponding to the four scientific concepts integrated into the prototype, as mentioned in Table I.

TABLE I. DESCRIPTION OF QUESTIONS AND CONCEPT SETS

Concept Set	Question No.	Concept Name
1	2,3,4	The Float Test
2	5,6,7	Paper Bag Magic
3	8,9,10	Save Green Vegetables
4	11,12,13	Car Screens/Shades

All the analysis is based on these four sets of questions. In each set, the leading question number was the critical question, and the following two questions were based on the first question of the collection. So, questions 3 and 4 were based on question 2. Questions 6 and 7 were based on question 5. Questions 9 and 10 were based on question 8. Moreover, Questions 12 and 13 were based on question 11.

All the essential questions were based on the previous knowledge of the concept. The question was used to measure the qualitative value of the interface between the user and the prototype. The main aim of the questions from the user is to know "How easily have users understood the concept behind the scientific discussion for the question?" and "How easily have users understood the concept behind the scientific discussion for question 2?". The same approach was applied to all sets of questions. Table II shows the exact analysis order of questions as per their category. It also relates the question sets with the main attributes of authentic learning. Table III provides the Questions set with their Measuring Parameters.

TABLE II. DESCRIPTION OF CONCEPT SETS WITH AUTHENTIC LEARNING ATTRIBUTES

Set	Provision of purpose	Exploration potential	Comprehensiveness	Field of study
1	Prompted the user if it knows the difference between a rotten and	The slide presented the user with an explanation and explanatory videos of the	The information was concise and very easy to understand.	The field of study in this real-world example is chemistry. The user learns about the physical and chemical

	healthy egg	idea.		properties of Hydrogen and sulfur.
2	Prompted the user if it knows how to ripen the fruits fast	The slide presented the user with explanations and explanatory videos of the idea.	The information was concise and very easy to understand.	The field of study in this set is chemistry. The user learns about Hydrogen and Carbon.
3	Prompted the user if it knows how to stop the vegetables turning into slug-green while cooking.	The slide presented the user with an explanation and explanatory videos of the concept.	The information was concise and very easy to understand.	In this set, the field of study in Chemistry. The user learns about the physicochemical properties of Magnesium.
4	Prompted the user if it knows why people use screen shades /screens in cars	The slide presented the user with explanations and explanatory videos of the idea.	The information was concise and very easy to understand.	The field of study in this set is biology and Chemistry. The user learns about greenhouse gasses.

TABLE III. QUESTIONS SET WITH MEASURING PARAMETERS

Question No.	Measuring
2,5,8,11	Prior understanding of the concept
3,6,9,12	The extent of ease of understanding the concept via Authentic Lab
4,7,10,13	The extent of remembering the concept

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Newman and his fellows presented the standards for authentic learning instruction and its assessment. These standards scrutinized higher-order thinking, knowledge depth, and relevance to the outside world [48]. According to the authors [5, 49], differentiators are required as an essential part of the active, authentic learning domain. The differentiators can comprise unique communication, and they build an understanding of the concept. Based on the presented studies, two parameters were established to be researched in this study. These two parameters include perception and memory retention of concepts. Understanding of ideas is also considered a primary requirement of authentic learning by researchers [28, 36, 46, 47]. Also, remember plays a vital role in the retention of concepts to be used later in a problem-solving scenario. Table IV provides the parameters considered and their corresponding questions added in the survey. The data was analyzed by counting the frequency to each of the responses and calculating the percentages. The Likert scale scores were analyzed by ANOVA using PROC GLM of SAS 9.4 (SAS Institute, Cary NC, USA) (Westfall et al., 2011).

TABLE IV. PARAMETERS AND CORRESPONDING QUESTIONS

Parameters	Corresponding Questions
The extent of ease of understanding P1	Q.03
	Q.06
	Q.09
	Q.12
The extent of numbering concept P2	Q.04
	Q.07
	Q.10
	Q.13

V. RESULTS

A survey was piloted at the University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia, to measure the usefulness of an authentic learning-based e-learning framework. Of the initial cohort of 98 students who participated in the survey, 89 (90.82%) completed the whole survey, and 09 of these (9.18%) partly filled the survey. Only students aged between 18 to 38 years, from different academic levels, bachelors, masters, and PhD participated in the study. **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the summary statistics of age groups and education levels of respondents.

Figure 1. Description of respondents by the educational level

Figure 2. Description of classification of respondents by age group

Most participants who responded with the prior learning experience of e-learning application came from the age group

23-27 years old. Overall, 44 respondents exhibited that they had used an e-learning application before, and minority (12) of participants indicated no experience of such an application. The second dominant age group with previous e-learning experience was 18-22. Regarding academic background, most of the respondents with prior e-learning experience came from the bachelor's program, shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. The second group, with the majority, in terms of prior e-learning experience, was masters with 11%.

A. Ease of Understanding and Remembering the Concept

Error! Reference source not found. illustrates the report of respondents on the prior learning experience of the concepts presented in the authentic lab prototype. According to the figure, 12 majorities of the respondents (73%) had no prior knowledge, and only 25% had a previous understanding of these concepts. As shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**, 73% of the respondent had no prior experience of using an app for e-learning purposes. Considering this lack of prior experience, the level of understanding gave promising results in **Error! Reference source not found.**, where 31% of the respondents found it very easy to understand the concepts, and 48% of respondents found it somewhat easy to understand the concepts presented in the application. It gives 79% of the respondents with a real understanding of the concept. For the third parameter of measurement "likeliness to remember the concept learned via Authentic Lab," the results are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 3. Percentage of respondents on ease understanding the concept

Figure 4. Description of respondents on prior experience

Figure 5. Percentage of respondents on likeliness to remember the concept

When the users of the prototype were asked about the "likelihood of remembering the concept," there were mixed responses. On a Likert scale one being, "will not be able to remember at all" and five being "can remember partially," most of the responses gave positive feedback. There were no students on scale 1, indicating that all the students assimilated the concept to some extent. The number of respondents understanding the concept was 92%, with a value of 4 on a scale of 5. The number is entirely aligned with the nature of the study that advocates a higher learning rate under an authentic learning environment. A comprehensive analysis of parameters against the age, prior experience, and level of education was run, and the following results were found. All four concepts are shown here as a concept set corresponding to the questions of the survey. For example, question 2 asked if the user knew how to tell the difference between healthy and rotten eggs. According to the concept set, question 3 was based on measuring the ease of understanding the concept, and question 4 was based on measuring the "likelihood to remember" the concept. The subcategories (ease/remember) in Table V are short names for the concept set questions.

VI. DISCUSSION

The authentic learning environment has many characteristics, namely real-world relevance, sustained investigation, various resources and perspectives, collaboration, reflection, integrated assessment. In the current study, only a few attributes were integrated into the Authentic Lab, resulting in the testing of those elements alone. The characteristics like provision of purpose, exploration potential, and their integration into the application prototype are discussed. It seems from the Table V that on comparing the ease of understanding and extent of remembering the concept among participants having prior experience and no prior experience, the inexperienced participants experienced the same level of ease of understanding. They rated similar levels of likelihood of remembering the concepts. The results, as shown in Table V, indicate that the app was user-friendly and was easy enough for inexperienced users to use it as efficiently as experienced users. No significant difference between participants of different ages, experience, and education level was found in the measured parameters. On average, all parameters were ranked by the

participants above score three on a five-point Likert scale showing a favourable response to the usage of the app and a satisfactory level of effectiveness of the app in teaching concepts based on the principles of authentic learning.

The p-value in the above table signifies the statistical significance where a smaller (typically ≤ 0.05) value indicates a positive sign against the theory, while a more significant value indicates weak evidence against the theory. A marginal p-value leaves the decision on the decision-maker as to what the conclusion is. In the results, the significant result of the p-value appeared in remembering the fruit concept in the category of education. The reason for such significant results can be that this question was most difficult for all the participants, and that might be the reason that the significant result appeared in the category of education because higher education levels can help understand and remember the problematic concepts relatively quickly. The p-values of other attributes show a firm agreement with the hypothesis and signify the importance of e-learning in an authentic domain.

TABLE V. COMPARISON OF PARAMETERS AGAINST AGE, EXPERIENCE, AND EDUCATIONS

Main Effects	Egg		Fruit		Vegetable		Screens	
	Ease	Remember	Ease	Remember	Ease	Remember	Ease	Remember
Age								
18-22	3.53 ± 0.31	4.39 ± 0.24	3.94 ± 0.33	3.91 ± 0.29	4.51 ± 0.32	4.92 ± 0.28	4.43 ± 0.31	4.55 ± 0.25
23-27	3.76 ± 0.30	4.52 ± 0.23	3.94 ± 0.32	3.95 ± 0.28	4.55 ± 0.31	4.96 ± 0.27	4.31 ± 0.29	4.50 ± 0.24
28-32	4.40 ± 0.32	4.67 ± 0.25	3.95 ± 0.34	3.92 ± 0.31	4.22 ± 0.33	4.53 ± 0.29	4.12 ± 0.32	4.38 ± 0.26
33-37	4.19 ± 0.50	4.04 ± 0.40	3.43 ± 0.54	2.90 ± 0.48	3.91 ± 0.52	4.03 ± 0.46	4.32 ± 0.50	4.09 ± 0.40
P-Value	0.2040	0.3502	0.8325	0.2359	0.7504	0.3975	0.8373	0.8362
Experience								
May be	4.12 ± 0.55	4.49 ± 0.43	3.63 ± 0.59	2.74 ± 0.52	4.66 ± 0.57	5.06 ± 0.50	4.13 ± 0.55	3.98 ± 0.44
No	3.82 ± 0.16	4.36 ± 0.13	3.91 ± 0.18	4.18 ± 0.16	4.14 ± 0.17	4.51 ± 0.15	4.39 ± 0.16	4.65 ± 0.13
Yes	3.98 ± 0.16	4.36 ± 0.13	3.91 ± 0.18	4.08 ± 0.16	4.10 ± 0.17	4.26 ± 0.15	4.38 ± 0.16	4.51 ± 0.13
P-Value	0.4146	0.9560	0.5227	0.9463	0.2833	0.1386	0.2677	0.7407
Education								
Masters	3.95 ± 0.29	4.36 ± 0.23	3.91 ± 0.31	3.61 ± 0.28	4.18 ± 0.30	4.42 ± 0.27	4.05 ± 0.29	4.36 ± 0.23
PhD	3.68 ± 0.42	4.42 ± 0.33	3.97 ± 0.45	3.72 ± 0.40	4.79 ± 0.43	5.18 ± 0.38	4.81 ± 0.42	4.55 ± 0.34
Undergrad	4.29 ± 0.28	4.43 ± 0.22	3.55 ± 0.30	3.68 ± 0.27	3.92 ± 0.29	4.23 ± 0.26	4.03 ± 0.28	4.23 ± 0.22
P-Value	0.5939	0.9556	0.8925	0.0253	0.6181	0.1496	0.8888	0.2359

VII. CONCLUSION

This study signifies the application of authentic principles in the domain of e-learning frameworks. Among many attributes of authentic learning, the “use of real-world problems” to relate the concepts was used. The combination of e-learning with an authentic approach leads to the design and development of a prototype that presented the user motivation to learn the concepts, provided exploration potential, and exhibited comprehensive information. After getting the respondents to use the prototype, an online survey form was presented that was designed with two main parameters repeating over the four sets of questions. These parameters include the ease of understanding the concept (P1) and the likelihood of remembering the concepts (P2). These parameters were analyzed against factors like age,

prior experience of any e-learning application, and educational level of the respondent. Analysis of the data showed that both parameters against the given factors showed positive results. There was no substantial alteration in the results across all the factors. It is obvious to conclude that age, prior experience, and educational level do not have any impact on the ease of understanding the concept and perception of the likelihood of remembering the concepts.

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